

On a remark from John von Neumann applicable to the symmetry induced turbulent scaling laws generated by the new theory of Oberlack et al.

Based on the findings [1, Section 5] and [2, Section 5] supported by the publications [3–5],[†] a clear mismatch between theory and numerical experiment is observed.

The theory developed in [9–14] on generating turbulent scaling laws in being induced by so-called “new statistical symmetries” shows several analytical shortcomings and physical inconsistencies which clearly become visible when comparing to DNS data [15, 16]: Those scaling laws which involve any parameters from the “new statistical symmetries” fail to predict the correct DNS multi-point correlations behavior beyond the second order[‡] [1, 2, Section 5] — the reason for this failure is found in the fact that these new symmetries violate the classical principle of cause and effect [1–3, 17]. Because as soon as these unphysical group parameters are removed, the matching to the DNS data improves by several orders of magnitude and becomes well-defined again for all orders n , which eventually is a clear indication that the new statistical symmetries developed in [9–14] are unphysical.

To say that these turbulent scaling laws are “clearly validated”, as claimed by Oberlack et al., e.g. in their latest review article [13], is therefore based on a fallacy. The problem is that this “validation” is always only performed for the lowest order moments, which, of course, can always be matched to the DNS data satisfactorily since there are enough free group parameters available to be fitted. This circumstance strongly reminds us of the situation which led to the famous remark done by John von Neumann many years ago (as quoted by Enrico Fermi to Freeman Dyson, see e.g. [18]):

*“With four parameters I can fit an elephant,
and with five I can make him wiggle his trunk.”*

But, as soon as the higher order correlations functions get fitted, not enough free parameters are available anymore and the curve-fitting procedure consistently fails if one tries to match these new turbulent scaling functions proposed by Oberlack et al. to DNS data. As already said, this outcome is supported by a mathematical proof given in [1, Appendix D] or [19, Appendix A]. Independent of the particular flow configuration, this proof clearly shows that the Lie-group based turbulent scaling laws for all higher order velocity correlations as derived in [9–14] are *not* consistent to the scaling of the lowest order correlation function, which for shear flows is of course the mean velocity field. In other words, the proof in [1] shows that for the lowest correlation order $n = 1$ no contradiction exists, only as from $n \geq 2$ onwards the contradiction starts, i.e., while the mean velocity field can be robustly matched to the DNS data, it consistently fails for all higher order correlation functions and gets more pronounced the higher the correlation order n is — while for $n = 2$ appropriate tools from statistical data analysis are still needed to detect this failure, the matching failure for the next higher order $n = 3$ is already so pronounced that no further analysis is actually needed.

Hence, by always only matching or comparing the DNS data to the lowest or next to lowest order velocity correlations of a specific turbulent flow, as it was done particularly in [10, 11, 13, 20–30], i.e. by matching or comparing only to the mean velocity profile and some profiles of the Reynolds stresses for wall-bounded (shear) flows, or only to the two-point velocity correlation for isotropic flows, is definitely not enough to be a true validation of the Lie-group based scaling theory. In particular, as this theory by Oberlack et al. which specifically considers the infinite (unclosed) system of *all* multi-point correlation

[†]To our comments [3–5], please also see our reactions [6–8], respectively.

[‡]Particularly in [1, Section 5] we demonstrate that already the second order is experiencing severe matching problems when using the appropriate tools from statistical data analysis.

equations and which thus is designed and laid-out to be a scaling theory for *all* higher order velocity correlations, special attention has to be devoted to the prediction value of all those correlation functions which go beyond the lowest or next to the lowest order. And exactly this has been investigated in [1, 2, Section 5], which then gives a completely different picture than the “validation” procedure in [10, 11, 13, 20–30] is trying to suggest. Hence, these “new statistical symmetries” need to be discarded as they will only unnecessarily lead to erroneous conclusions in the theory of turbulence.

References

- [1] M. Frewer, G. Khujadze, and H. Foysi, “On the physical inconsistency of a new statistical scaling symmetry in incompressible Navier-Stokes turbulence,” *arXiv:1412.3061*, 2014.
- [2] G. Khujadze and M. Frewer, “Revisiting the Lie-group symmetry method for turbulent channel flow with wall transpiration,” *arXiv:1606.08396*, 2016.
- [3] M. Frewer, G. Khujadze, and H. Foysi, “Comment on “Statistical symmetries of the Lundgren-Monin-Novikov hierarchy”,” *Phys. Rev. E*, vol. 92, p. 067001, 2015.
- [4] M. Frewer, G. Khujadze, and H. Foysi, “Comment on “Application of the extended Lie group analysis to the Hopf functional formulation of the Burgers equation”,” *J. Math. Phys.*, vol. 57, p. 034102, 2016.
- [5] M. Frewer and G. Khujadze, “Comments on Janocha *et al.* Lie symmetry analysis of the Hopf functional-differential equation”,” *Symmetry*, vol. 8, no. 4, p. 23, 2016.
- [6] M. Frewer, G. Khujadze, and H. Foysi, “Objections to a Reply of Oberlack *et al.*,” *ResearchGate*, pp. 1–9, 2015.
- [7] M. Frewer, G. Khujadze, and H. Foysi, “On a new technical error in a further Reply by Oberlack *et al.* and its far-reaching effect on their original study,” *ResearchGate*, pp. 1–6, 2016.
- [8] M. Frewer and G. Khujadze, “An example of how a methodological mistake aggravates erroneous results when only correcting the results and not the method itself,” *ResearchGate*, pp. 1–10, 2016.
- [9] M. Oberlack and A. Rosteck, “New statistical symmetries of the multi-point equations and its importance for turbulent scaling laws,” *Discrete Continuous Dyn. Syst.*, vol. Ser. S 3, pp. 451–471, 2010.
- [10] M. Oberlack and A. Zieleniewicz, “Statistical symmetries and its impact on new decay modes and integral invariants of decaying turbulence,” *Journal of Turbulence*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 4–22, 2013.
- [11] V. Avsarkisov, M. Oberlack, and S. Hoyas, “New scaling laws for turbulent Poiseuille flow with wall transpiration,” *J. Fluid Mech.*, vol. 746, pp. 99–122, 2014.
- [12] M. Waławczyk, N. Staffolani, M. Oberlack, A. Rosteck, M. Wilczek, and R. Friedrich, “Statistical symmetries of the Lundgren-Monin-Novikov hierarchy,” *Phys. Rev. E*, vol. 90, no. 1, p. 013022, 2014.
- [13] M. Oberlack, M. Waławczyk, A. Rosteck, and V. Avsarkisov, “Symmetries and their importance for statistical turbulence theory,” *Mechanical Engineering Reviews*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 15–157, 2015.
- [14] D. D. Janocha, M. Waławczyk, and M. Oberlack, “Lie symmetry analysis of the Hopf functional-differential equation,” *Symmetry*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 1536–1566, 2015.

- [15] M. P. Simens, J. Jiménez, S. Hoyas, and Y. Mizuno, “A high-resolution code for turbulent boundary layers,” *J. Comp. Phys.*, vol. 228, pp. 4218–4231, 2009.
- [16] G. Borrell, J. A. Sillero, and J. Jiménez, “A code for direct numerical simulation of turbulent boundary layers at high Reynolds numbers in BG/P supercomputers,” *Comp. & Fluids*, vol. 80, pp. 37–43, 2013.
- [17] M. Frewer, G. Khujadze, and H. Foysi, “A note on the notion “statistical symmetry”,” [arXiv:1602.08039](https://arxiv.org/abs/1602.08039), 2016.
- [18] F. Dyson, “A meeting with Enrico Fermi: How one intuitive physicist rescued a team from fruitless research,” *Nature*, vol. 427, no. 6972, p. 297, 2004.
- [19] M. Frewer, G. Khujadze, and H. Foysi, “A critical examination of the statistical symmetries admitted by the Lundgren-Monin-Novikov hierarchy of unconfined turbulence,” [arXiv:1412.6949](https://arxiv.org/abs/1412.6949), 2014.
- [20] M. Oberlack and A. Rosteck, “Turbulent scaling laws and what we can learn from the multi-point correlation equations,” *Proceedings of the 7th International Symposium on Turbulence and Shear Flow Phenomena (TSFP-7)*, Ottawa, 2011.
- [21] M. Oberlack and A. Rosteck, “Applications of the new symmetries of the multi-point correlation equations,” *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 318, no. 4, p. 042011, 2011.
- [22] V. S. Avsarkisov and M. Oberlack, “New scaling laws for turbulent Poiseuille flow with wall transpiration,” *Proceedings of the 8th International Symposium on Turbulence and Shear Flow Phenomena (TSFP-8)*, Poitiers, 2013.
- [23] A. Rosteck and M. Oberlack, “New turbulent scaling laws from the multi-point correlation equations,” *14th European Turbulence Conference (ETC-14)*, Lyon, 2013.
- [24] V. Avsarkisov, M. Oberlack, S. Hoyas, and G. Khujadze, “New mean velocity scaling laws for turbulent Poiseuille flow with wall transpiration,” *14th European Turbulence Conference (ETC-14)*, Lyon, 2013.
- [25] M. Oberlack, A. Rosteck, and V. Avsarkisov, “Can we obtain first principle results for turbulence statistics?,” *International Conference on Heat Transfer, Fluid Mechanics and Thermodynamics (HEFAT)*, Orlando, 2014.
- [26] V. Avsarkisov, M. Oberlack, S. Hoyas, A. Rosteck, J. P. Garcia-Galache, and A. Frank, “Plane turbulent Couette flow: DNS, large scale structures and symmetry induced scaling laws,” *Proceedings of the 9th International Symposium on Turbulence and Shear Flow Phenomena (TSFP-9)*, Melbourne, 2015.
- [27] A. Rosteck and M. Oberlack, “New turbulent scaling laws from the multi-point correlation equations,” *Proceedings of the 9th International Symposium on Turbulence and Shear Flow Phenomena (TSFP-9)*, Melbourne, 2015.
- [28] S. Hoyas, S. V. Kraheberger, and M. Oberlack, “Turbulent plane Couette flow with wall-transpiration,” *15th European Turbulence Conference (ETC-15)*, Delft, 2015.
- [29] S. Kraheberger, M. Oberlack, and S. Hoyas, “Scaling laws of turbulent Couette flow with wall-normal transpiration,” *Bulletin of the American Physical Society*, vol. 60, 2015.
- [30] S. Hoyas, S. Kraheberger, and M. Oberlack, “DNS of turbulent Couette flow with transpiration - spectra and symmetry induced scaling laws,” *Bulletin of the American Physical Society*, vol. 61, 2016.